

OAPEN foundation

2020
annual report

OAPEN Foundation Annual Report 2020

Key results and developments

Highlights of 2020

In 2020, the OAPEN Foundation celebrated its 10 year anniversary as an open infrastructure service for open access (OA) books, providing services to publishers, libraries, and research funders in the areas of hosting, deposit, quality assurance, dissemination, and digital preservation. The mission of OAPEN to increase discoverability of OA books and to build trust around OA books has been leading us through a challenging year marked by the COVID-19 pandemic.

As a non-profit foundation operating fully open and global infrastructure services for open access books, we rely entirely on the financial goodwill of the community for us to return useful services to academic libraries, research funders, and open access publishers. As open infrastructures selected by SCOSS (The Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services) OAPEN and DOAB have attracted more support from institutions and consortia across the globe. Although we still have not yet reached our financial target, the increased support has been immensely helpful to maintain our services and to engage further with the community.

We wish to thank all those institutions, funders, and publishers who have supported the services of the OAPEN Foundation – the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), the OAPEN Library, and the OAPEN OA Books Toolkit – in 2020. This support has helped us sustain and improve our operations. During the year we have onboarded many new publishers, added thousands of books to our services, migrated both our platforms to the open source environment, DSpace 6, launched a new OA books toolkit for authors, co-founded an OA books network and engaged actively in international projects and conversations around open access books through talks at conferences and webinars, and via blog posts, articles and tweets.

In this report we will explain in more detail some of these key achievements of 2020.

The OAPEN Library

In 2020 the OAPEN Library (<http://library.oapen.org>) migrated to the open source DSpace 6 platform. All books in the OAPEN Library are available for direct download without any cost or registration requirements for the user. Almost 5,000 books were added to the library during 2020, increasing the total number of open access books to over 15,000.

The OAPEN Library is being used worldwide. In 2020 we saw a dramatic growth of downloads from the OAPEN Library. We suspect that the increase is caused by several factors, as explained below.

OAPEN Library: Number of Downloads

Downloads from the OAPEN Library increased by 77% in 2020. The collection enlarged from over 9,000 titles in October 2019 to over 13,500 titles in October 2020. In other words, it became 1.5 times larger, while the number of downloads doubled. We saw more downloads per book on average.

77% increase of downloads from the OAPEN Library

OAPEN: Downloads Worldwide

Top Three Countries with most downloads: United States, Germany, United Kingdom

OAPEN: Growth of Titles and Publishers

4,682 new titles added in the OAPEN library in 2020, now exceeding 15,000 books

Firstly, we welcomed more publishers in the OAPEN Library increasing the number of new titles significantly. Secondly, COVID-19 has undoubtedly meant that more users have searched for digital books due to the lockdowns of physical libraries in most parts of the world. Thirdly, the migration of the OAPEN Library to the open source DSpace platform seems to have boosted our dissemination due to more and improved ways of integrating the OAPEN Library into library catalogues and due to improved metadata exchanges with library intermediaries such as OCLC and ExLibris and Google Scholar.

OAPEN Library: Languages and Licences in 2020

The books in the OAPEN Library come with different licences. The licence information is clearly displayed and included in the metadata. An increasing number of books carry the most open licence, the Creative Commons CC BY licence. This provides the user with full re-usage rights to the book under the condition that the author is given proper attribution. This, for instance, makes text and data mining of the book possible.

As an infrastructure for OA books, the OAPEN Library helps publishers to disseminate, preserve, and monitor usage of their books, libraries to make them available to their patrons and funders to organise and monitor the books they fund. While all of this is true and important, we should not forget that the OAPEN Library is also in itself a rich source of exciting books for anyone to explore. All books are free for all to download and read without any payment or registration, **a truly open library.**

Most downloaded books from the OAPEN Library in 2020

Exciting books for anyone to explore, free for all to download

The Directory of Open Access Books

*Open metadata
for over 40,000 OA
books from more
than 500 publishers*

OAPEN Foundation also operates the international indexing service, the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB, <http://doabooks.org>) together with OpenEdition. Developed in 2012, DOAB is increasingly becoming an international hub for OA books providing open metadata (CC0) for over 40,000 OA books from more than 500 publishers.

DOAB is free to use for libraries and publishers and anyone else. Users don't even need to register to explore the richness of the catalogue. Publishers need to comply with the requirements for peer review and open licensing based on existing OASPA membership criteria. In 2021, this will be further developed when introducing the DOAB Certification Service which is developed as part of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure. Supported by an independent Scientific Committee, this Certification Service will display the peer review procedures of the publishers thereby increasing transparency around quality assurance of open access books.

In 2020, a migration of DOAB to the open source DSpace 6 platform was prepared and successfully implemented in early 2021. DOAB now offers libraries and other institutions a variety of options for easy integration of the directory in their catalogues. Metadata are provided in several formats including MARC, CSV, RIS and ONIX. It is also possible to search the directory using a REST API and the directory can be harvested using OAI-PMH.

Libraries and other institutions (including research funders) can support the operation and development of DOAB through our membership programme and publishers can support DOAB through our sponsorship programme. We wish to thank all our supporters and sponsors immensely for your contributions in 2020.

DOAB: Growth of Titles and Publishers

78 publishers and 8,520 new titles were added to DOAB in 2020

DOAB: Languages and Licenses in 2020

OAPEN OA Books Toolkit

Open Access Books Network

In the autumn of 2020, OAPEN launched the OAPEN OA Books Toolkit¹ to help book authors, libraries and research support teams to better understand open access book publishing and to increase trust in open access books. At the day of launch the toolkit comprised over 30 articles about OA books written by experts in the field. It is a global and stakeholder agnostic initiative. A broad and diverse Editorial Advisory Board is involved in the development and maintenance of the toolkit, including authors, publishers, research support staff, funders, and other key stakeholders.

The toolkit was developed in close collaboration with Springer Nature and the University of Glasgow, with support from the universities of Oxford, Glasgow and Utrecht, who hosted a series of workshops during the development stage. The toolkit is operated by OAPEN.

In its first half year of existence, the toolkit has already seen around 30,000 unique visits from 144 countries and it has been well received by institutions across the board.

Together with OPERAS, Scholar-led and SPARC Europe, OAPEN launched the Open Access Books Network² in October 2020. The Open Access Books Network is a space for conversations and events about OA books for all stakeholders in the field. The network is driven by in-kind contributions from the community. The OAPEN community manager is one of its three coordinators.

¹ <https://oabooks-toolkit.org/>

² <https://hcommons.org/groups/open-access-books-network/>

Community engagement

OAPEN actively engages with its community and is an active participant in global conversations on open access books. In 2020, OAPEN and DOAB organised and participated in events such as (virtual) conferences, webinar sessions, workshops and a podcast. Additionally, OAPEN and DOAB use its communication channels to inform and engage with its community, through its regular blog posts, (news) articles and tweets in 2020 for instance.

14 blogs
10k+ blog visits

1271 new followers
11k+ total followers
427k tweet views

14 newsletters
3274 total subscribers
346 new subscribers

21 events

Community - testimonials

Another brilliant open access book out thanks to [@AmsterdamUPress](#) & [@OAPENbooks](#):
SCREEN SPACE RECONFIGURED is the first edited volume that critically and theoretically examines the many novel renderings of space brought to us by 21st century screens. <http://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500>.

Más de mil quinientos libros de historia, online y gratuitos, en [@OAPENbooks](#)

We are delighted to announce that ALL the books by the ScholarLed presses are now available in a shared collection on [@OAPENbooks](#)! There are over 500 #OpenAccess books to browse -- view and download them all freely here: <https://oapen.org/topic/15632108-scholarled> #OAbooks #ScalingSmall

Replying to [@SN_OAbooks](#) and [@OAPENbooks](#)
Thank you [@Eelco](#) and team for this toolkit. As a publisher and author it gonna guide us on how to execute oa publishing exercises. It's my desire that my institution's publishing department adopts OA model now that there's a developed toolkit! Thanks

Would like to thank [@OAPENbooks](#)
[@oabooksnetwork](#) w/introduction to [@scossfunding](#) for helping me find & access a book for #MedicalAnthropology reading. Just another example of the wonderful European Union!
#OpenAccess #education #publicgoods #publichealth

Project activities

OAPEN also participated in several international projects and initiatives:

OPERAS Research Infrastructure (EU)	operas-eu.org
ENABLE! (DE)	enable-oa.org
OPERAS-P project (EU)	operas.hypotheses.org
TRIPLE project (EU)	gotriple.eu
Community-led Open Publication Infra-structures for Monographs (COPIM) (UK)	copim.ac.uk
Open Access eBook Usage (OAeBU) Data Trust pilot project (US)	educopia.org/data_trust
SCELC & OAPEN Pilot Project (US)	scelc.libguides.com/scelc-oapen
European Research Council (ERC-OAPEN-2019)	cordis.europa.eu/projects

ENABLE!
Bibliotheken, Verlage und Autor*innen für
Open Access in den Social Sciences und Humanities

OPERAS: Grant agreement 731031, 731102, 871069, 863420
OPERAS-P: Grant Agreement 871069
TRIPLE: Grant Agreement 863420
ERC: Grant Agreement: 964352

Governance

The OAPEN Foundation is a not-for-profit organisation based in the Netherlands, with its registered office at the National Library in The Hague. OAPEN is dedicated to open access, peer-reviewed books.

OAPEN operates three platforms:

OAPEN Library - a central repository for hosting and disseminating OA books

OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit - a toolkit on OA book publishing for authors

Directory of Open Access Books - a discovery service indexing OA books, in partnership with OpenEdition

OAPEN (Open Access Publishing in European Networks) was developed as a 30-month targeted project co-funded by the EU in its eContentplus-program (2008-2010). The goal of the project was to achieve a sustainable publication model for academic books in humanities and social sciences and to improve the visibility and usability of high quality academic research in Europe. After the close of the project, OAPEN continued its activities as a foundation.

OAPEN Foundation was established by the University of Amsterdam (UvA), the University of Leiden (UL), the University Library of Utrecht University (UU), the Netherlands Academy of Sciences (KNAW), the National Library of the Netherlands (KB) and Amsterdam University Press (AUP).

The OAPEN Foundation Board of Directors

In 2020 there has been a change in the organisational structure of the OAPEN Foundation. Since the start of OAPEN the founding members formed a council of participants which appointed the board members and approved the budget and the annual report. With the new membership programme such a council was no longer appropriate. It will

be replaced by an advisory board with an advisory role and the right to appoint one board member of the Board of Directors. The other members of the board of directors will be appointed by the board itself. After the corresponding change of the statutes two new board members have been appointed.

The OAPEN Foundation Board of Directors consists of the following members:

Bas Savenije, *Chair*

Kurt De Belder, *Secretary* – Leiden University

Reinier Groen, *Treasurer*

Antia Wiersma – Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences

The OAPEN Foundation team

On the last day of 2020 Eelco Ferwerda retired as director of the OAPEN Foundation having directed the OAPEN since its foundation and before that acted as coordinator of the OAPEN project. On the first day of 2021 Niels Stern took over as director of the OAPEN Foundation and Ronald Snijder was promoted as Deputy Director.

In the month of May Tom Mosterd was hired as Community Manager of DOAB and OAPEN focusing on community engagement, communication activities, and fundraising (in particular through the SCOSS campaign).

The OAPEN team as of 1 January 2021:

Niels Stern, *Director*
stern@oapen.org

Ronald Snijder, *Deputy Director*
r.snijder@oapen.org

Lotte Kruijt, *Project Manager*
l.kruijt@oapen.org

Dorien van der Giessen, *Collection Manager*
d.vandergiessen@oapen.org

Tom Mosterd, *Community Manager*
t.mosterd@oapen.org

Finances overview

In financial terms, we reached break-even in 2020 at 458,384 EUR.

2020 was special in the sense that we received substantial EU funding through the OPERAS-P project (Grant agreement ID: 871069) which was primarily spent on the successful migration of the OAPEN Library and the Directory of Open Access Books to DSpace 6.

Expenses 2020

Turnover 2020

Outlook 2021

We will continuously seek to fuel the community in ways that help promoting open access to books

A core task for the OAPEN team is to ensure a well-working OAPEN Library and DOAB and to grow the collections by adding more books and onboarding new publishers. It is essential that institutions and funders across the world can rely on the basic services that OAPEN provides. We will also continuously seek to fuel the community in ways that help promoting open access to books, for instance by operating and developing the OAPEN OA Books Toolkit and by engaging in the OA Books Network.

Funder OA books policy development

OAPEN will seek to be actively engaged in discussions around OA book policy developments. For instance, OAPEN has already helped UK Research and Innovation with a gap analysis and recommendations for infrastructures to support a policy for OA books. These recommendations are based on existing knowledge derived from other studies and from working closely with several European research funders who already have OA book policies in place. OAPEN is therefore well prepared to engage in discussions with cOAlition S around their proposed OA book statement (expected in 2021). The OAPEN Library and the Directory of Open Access Books should be useful tools for such large-scale policy implementation. We will work with all relevant actors in the community to ensure the best possible implementation of forthcoming policies for OA books.

Seeking sustainability for OAPEN and DOAB

We have already with some success been seeking support for our services from the library community worldwide. The SCOSS (The Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services) selection and recommendation to support DOAB and OAPEN jointly has been very helpful in this respect. However, while SCOSS as part of its mission will be announcing new infrastructures to be supported, we prepare to receive less support through SCOSS and therefore have begun a transitioning process where we now actively promote a combined

We will focus on increasing our support in the US and Germany

DOAB/OAPEN membership (as recommended by SCOSS)¹.

Moving forward, we will focus on increasing our support in regions that heavily use our services but are underrepresented in terms of contributions. OAPEN is currently not well supported in the U.S. and in Germany where we see the most usage of our services. Therefore, we have focused our efforts on these two major countries. In the U.S. we have entered a Memorandum of Understanding with LYRASIS to help us increase the number of U.S. members. In Germany, we use our network to disseminate the benefits of the OAPEN Library and DOAB at seminars and to key stakeholder groups. While we prioritise the U.S. and Germany, we also campaign in other countries while taking care of existing memberships.

It is important for us to stay in tune with the demands of the community and to be responsive to new needs. Therefore, we will be committed to continue our stakeholder engagement in 2021.

Yours sincerely,

Niels Stern
Director, OAPEN Foundation

May 2021

¹ <https://oapen.org/librarians/15963583-support-oapen-libraries>

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